

CANTEEN SERVICE QUALITY MONITORING AMONG SHS LEARNERS' SATISFACTION: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED FOOD MANAGEMENT POLICIES

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Abstract

Canteen operations and quality services ensure that learners' health and nutrition are the top priorities. To better analyze how the school canteen in the senior high school is operated, the study intended to describe the profile of the student-respondents based on their grade level; describe the problems in the operation of the school canteen in terms of sanitation, policies, and staff management; describe the level of learners satisfaction in terms of quality of food and quality of service; describe the importance of having a school canteen operated by the school; test differences in the respondent's perceptions towards the operation of the school canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables; test differences on the respondent's perceptions towards quality services provided by the canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables; test the relationship between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services; and propose a strategic plan for the operation of the school canteen. Using the descriptive survey design of quantitative research, the data were gathered from 126 respondents (60 Grade 11 and 66 Grade 12 students) via a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, and mean) and inferential statistics (ANOVA/F-test and Pearson r). The results indicated that there are (69) sixty-nine respondents who are from Grade 11 and Grade 12 of the SHS; the student-respondents agreed on the factors/contributors affecting the operation of the school canteen such as sanitation, policies, and staff management; the student-respondents are satisfied with the factors/contributors affecting the quality of school canteen services in terms of the assessment of food quality services and quality services; the student-respondents acknowledged the importance of having a school canteen in school operations, especially in serving the school community and providing nutritious and healthy meals; there are no significant differences in the respondent's perceptions towards the operation of the school canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables; there are no significant differences in the respondent's perceptions towards quality services provided by the canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables; there is a positive correlation between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services; and the study proposed a strategic plan to improve further the operation of the school canteen to cater to the needs of the clientele, especially the SHS students on its operation and services provided.

Keywords: Canteen service quality, learners' satisfaction, food management policies, food sanitation

Introduction

School canteens are essential in promoting students' health and nutrition, especially for Senior High School learners who spend long hours in school. Effective canteen operations require proper sanitation, clear policies, and efficient staff management. Learners' satisfaction with food and services reflects the overall quality of the canteen and its alignment with school health standards. This study seeks to assess the current operations and service quality of the school canteen, identify challenges, and explore how learners perceive these services. The goal is to develop a strategic plan to improve canteen operations based on student feedback. The study will benefit school administrators, canteen staff, and DepEd stakeholders by providing insights into canteen operations and student satisfaction. It will also guide improvements in canteen services and contribute to better student health, nutrition, and overall well-being.

Research Objectives

Nowadays, the school canteen faces different and huge problems since face-to-face classes have already begun. Being too crowded, having unwanted smells, and having insufficient things can result in various warnings and violations that lead to closure. This study aimed to create a monitoring tool that can lead to effective management policies in school canteens that will be aligned to the Senior High School Learners of Cabangan National High School, located at Cabangan, Zambales within the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions for an in-depth analysis of the main problem:

1. Describe the profile of the student-respondents based on their grade level.
2. Describe the problems in the operation of the school canteen in terms of:
 - 2.1 sanitation;
 - 2.2 policies; and
 - 2.3 staff management.
3. Describe the level of learners satisfaction in terms of:
 - 3.1 quality of food; and
 - 3.2 quality of service.
4. Describe the importance of having a school canteen operated by the school.
5. Test differences in the respondent's perceptions towards the operation of the school canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables.
6. Test differences on the respondent's perceptions towards quality services provided by the canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables
7. Test the relationship between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services.
8. Propose a strategic plan for the operation of the school canteen.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study would be favorable to the following authorities:

DepEd Officials. The findings of this study may be beneficial to them by increasing the number of seminars offered to school administrators to assist them in addressing problems with the management of the school canteen. This could result in a more productive working environment, one in which employees are both productive and contributive to the Department's efforts to realize its vision and fulfill its mission.

School Administrators. The findings of this study could provide them with useful information for improving the administration of the school cafeteria for the sake of the students. They might do so on a regular basis in order to find ways to improve their school cafeteria and devise cunning plans for working toward the achievement of their objective.

Teachers and Other School Staff. The findings of this study may assist them in administering the school canteen, particularly if it is a teacher's cooperative school.

Future Researchers. The results of this research may be used as a starting point for further investigation into other aspects that contribute to the management of a school canteen as well as the best practices that can be modified to address the issues that have been identified. Therefore, they may include other variables that they felt necessary in order to broaden the scope of this body of study.

Literature Review

A canteen is a location where you can dine and refuel. The canteen offers the nutritional needs a student requires to live with maximum energy, endurance, strength, and fortitude during the course of the school day. Every canteen has the responsibility to provide quality food with proper service and good hygiene practices to the customer (Galabo, 2019). Also, it is committed to providing clear communication between the school and canteen services to be able to keep positive relationships among teaching staff, students, and canteen personnel (Merriam-Webster Inc., 2014).

But students prefer more tasty and trendy food, so they eat a lot of fast food and instant snacks, which is affected by food commercials and convenience (The Food and Drug Association, 2007). Through the curriculum in schools and a variety of projects that give chances for physically fit people who love eating healthy food, the Department of Education is firmly committed to supporting students' health and well-being. With the increasing incidence of health concerns nowadays, schools should be serious about creating a healthy environment since pupils stay longer at school and buy food at school canteens. DepEd Order No. 13, series of 2017, also known as Policy and Guidelines on Healthy Food and Beverage Choices in Schools, was issued by the Department of Education in order to support the health needs of the patrons of every school in the Philippines (DepEd, 2017). The memo is in response to the mandate of Article II of Republic Act No. 6938 or the Act to Ordain a Cooperative Code of the Philippines (RA 6938, 1990). (RA 6938, 1990).

Comprehensive health and wellness initiatives, including food and nutrition instruction, are encouraged to be implemented in schools. In order for students, staff, and other school personnel to enjoy wholesome food at reasonable costs during the school day, it is crucial that the establishment and operation of the school canteen foster a passion and desire for eating wholesome food.

Schools are in a different position to develop healthy dietary behaviors. The school canteen should present options that support healthy nutrition. It must ensure that students consume the appropriate quantity of nutrient-rich foods while also avoiding restricting their food options. It is important that the food prepared by the school cafeteria contains all the nutrients needed by a student (Brener et al., 2009).

Satisfaction of employees and clients is an important element of success for any organization and any sector of the economy (Bay et al., 2014). Employees' service to customers has the strongest influence on relationship quality (Bencito, 2014). School canteens need to be productive and it can be evaluated through certain measures. These may include student support, the number of canteen workers, and profitability. Profit from the operations of a school canteen is often a significant source of revenue for a school. Therefore, it is of considerable importance that nutritious food items attract students and are supplied at a price affordable to the students, and that will contribute to their profit (Department of Education and Early Childhood Development, 2013).

However, according to UNICEF's report on the State of the World's Children: Children, Food and Nutrition, one in three Filipino children under the age of five are malnourished and stunted, wasted, or overweight, and two-thirds are at risk of malnutrition and hidden hunger as a result of their diets' poor quality (Noorani, 2019; Irader, 2022), revealed in her study that students preferred on buying ready-made food for their mealtimes two to three times per week from street food stalls and establishments because of a lack of time in preparing food. In order to prevent foodborne illnesses, which are typically brought on by unsafe food handling and preparation, it should be forbidden to purchase food outside of the school canteen.

Meals are served in the classrooms by schools without their own cafeterias, which has issues with a high risk of accidents during the movement of the meals, improper meal temperature, unclean status of meal provision, and serving students an uneven amount of food (Kim & Lee, 2004). However, even if there is a cafeteria in a school, the space is small, and waiting time for meals is prolonged making students unsatisfied (Lee, 2005).

Several factors can affect students' satisfaction with the canteen's foods and services including facilities and services. Providing good services and complete facilities and equipment give students a high level of satisfaction (Onate & Delelis, 2016; Samcio Martin, 2016). However, there are situations wherein canteens fail to meet the satisfaction of the pupils. Some students are forced not to buy in the canteen because of the different factors affecting their buying behavior, including food preferences, food prices, food quality, canteen services, and facilities and equipment. Some goods are so pricey that some college students cannot afford to purchase them. Students do not buy low-quality goods from businesses, and they detest subpar customer service. These factors contribute to certain students' lower satisfaction with the food and services provided by their canteen (Maddock et al., 2005).

For instance, many students say that the canteen's prices are too high, making it difficult for them to afford due to their meager allowances. A larger location for the canteen is also suggested by teachers and students because it is typically crowded. Regarding the type or variety of foods offered at the canteen, students have a variety of experiences and grievances. As a result, the researcher is given the task of conducting this study to evaluate the standard of the canteen services offered to learners at Cabangan High School, located at Cabangan, Zambales within the School Year 2024-2025, where the results would act as a mechanism for providing good and satisfactory canteen services.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive survey method of research in an attempt to analyze and interpret the Canteen service quality monitoring among SHS learners' satisfaction. This is a basis for proposed food management policies. The respondents of the study were the senior high school learners of Cabangan High School, located at Cabangan, Zambales during the School Year 2024-2025. Only the learners who were in the school during the data-gathering period comprised the respondents. A questionnaire was the main instrument used by the researcher in conducting this study.

Respondents of the Study

The participants in the study were SHS students from Cabangan HS, which has a total student population of 126. Both Grade 11 and Grade 12 students participated. The sample size with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 8% was calculated using www.raosoft.com, and it was determined that a total of 69 respondents were

required for the survey using a random sample calculator. As can be seen from the table, 60 or 47.62% are Grade 11 students and 66 or 52.38% are Grade 12 students.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Grade Level	Total HMSS	Total ABM	Total Population	% of Respondents
11	36	24	60	47.62
12	36	30	66	52.38
Total			126	100.00

Research Instrument

The following research instruments were used in the gathering of data and information for the study. The researchers made a survey questionnaire distributed to the respondents using google form which consisted of three parts, namely: (1) Describe the problems in the operation of the school canteen in terms of sanitation; policies; and staff management; (2) Describe the level of learner’s satisfaction in terms of quality of food and quality of service and (3) Describe the importance of having a school canteen operated by the school. Since the survey questionnaire was made by the researcher, a reliability test was conducted. A dry run was conducted on 20 students who were not part of the final pool of respondents. Their responses were then subjected to a Cronbach Alpha reliability test. The overall value of Part I was .930, Part II .858, and Part III .766 which indicates a very good level of reliability.

The form was scored with a Four-point Likert scale. The following norms of interpretation on the problems in the operation of the school canteen were used:

Scale	Range Interval	Descriptive Equivalent
4	3.36 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly disagree

The following norms of interpretation on the level of learners’ satisfaction were used:

Scale	Range Interval	Descriptive Equivalent
4	3.36 – 4.00	Very Satisfied
3	2.51 – 3.25	Satisfied
2	1.76 – 2.50	Unsatisfied
1	1.00 – 1.75	Very Unsatisfied

The following norms of interpretation on the importance of having a school canteen operated by the school:

Scale	Range Interval	Descriptive Equivalent
4	3.36 – 4.00	Very Important
3	2.51 – 3.25	Important
2	1.76 – 2.50	Slightly Important

1	1.00 – 1.75	Unimportant
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Data Collection

As the basis for a proposed food management policy, this study employed a survey questionnaire to investigate the canteen service quality monitoring among senior high school students' satisfaction. The data collection technique for the study was undertaken based on the researchers' and participants' availability. The researchers distributed the survey surveys using Google Form. Links were generated and then emailed to respondents via Facebook Messenger. Respondents provide their responses using the form, which are then recorded, saved, and retrieved by the researchers. The time allocated to respondents by the researcher to complete the questionnaire represented the respondents' availability. The confidentiality of respondents was ensured.

Ethical Considerations

To officially perform the study, the researchers sent and received all relevant letters and permits. Google forms were utilized to request that respondents complete the questionnaires. Respondents were instructed with great caution and specificity to ensure the confidentiality of the collected data. Throughout the data collection process, the anonymity of respondents and their responses was emphasized in order to protect the sensitive and crucial information gathered from respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistical approaches such as measuring the mean and standard deviation were used. The frequency and percentage were utilized to analyze the respondent profile. The measured and weighted mean factors and contributors that affect Operation of School Canteen in terms of sanitation; policies; and staff management; the level of learner's satisfaction in terms of the quality of food and the quality of service; and the significance of having a school canteen that is operated by the school on the Likert-scale employed from the questionnaire. Meanwhile, analysis of variance was used to investigate the variations in the respondent's opinion of the functioning of the school canteen of Students-respondents when grouped according to Grade level profile variables. The Pearson r correlation test was utilized to investigate the possible connection between the successful running of the school canteen and the level of service provided by the canteen.

Findings

This section presents the gathered and processed data using a tabular form, analyzed and provide interpretations to give a clear and better understanding of the problem.

Findings

1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' profile variables of grade levels.

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	f	%	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Grade 11	33	47.8	48	47.8
Grade 12	36	52.2	52	100.0
Total	69	100.0	100.0	

For grade levels profile, out of (69) sixty-nine respondents, there are 33 or 48.00% are Grade 11; 36 or 52.00% are Grade 12, respectively.

2. Factors/Contributors Affecting the Operation of the School Canteen

2.1 Sanitation

Table 3 shows the perception of the respondents towards sanitation affecting the operation of the school canteen.

Table 3
Perception towards Sanitation Affecting the Operation of the School Canteen

Statement Indicator	WM	QI	Rank
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1. Does the school canteen have sanitation Clearance/Permit from the local Health Department?	3.21	A	4
2. Does the school canteen have available portable drinking water and hand washing facilities?	3.22	A	3
3. Does the school administration maintain the cleanliness and orderliness of the canteen premises?	3.28	SA	1
4. Does school canteen personnel/staff wear clean and proper attire at all times?	3.10	A	5
5. Does the school canteen do hygienic practices on food preparation, cooking display, serving, and storage?	3.24	A	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.21	A	

The respondents "Strongly agree" on indicator 3, "Does the school administration maintain the cleanliness and orderliness of the canteen premises?", manifested in its high mean value of 3.28 and ranked 1st while the least was indicator 4, "Does school canteen personnel/staff wear clean and proper attire at all times?", with mean of 3.10 interpreted as "agree" and ranked 5th. Overall, the responses towards sanitation obtained a weighted mean of 3.21 with the qualitative interpretation of "agree".

2.2 Policies

Table 4 shows the perception of the respondents towards Policies affecting the operation of the school canteen.

Table 4
Perception towards Policies Affecting Operation of School Canteen

Statement Indicator	WM	QI	Rank
1. Does the school administration implement a pricing policy to be affordable?	3.15	A	1
2. Does the school canteen was supplied with enough chairs and tables for its operation?	2.87	A	5
3. Does the school administer a screening policy for hiring food handlers and staff of the school canteen?	3.13	A	2
4. Does the school canteen regularly subject to inspection to ensure standards of operation?	3.03	A	3
5. Does the implemented policy on school canteen operations to cater patrons operating smoothly?	3.01	A	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.04	A	

The respondents "Agree" on indicator 1, "Does the school administration implement a pricing policy to be affordable?", manifested in its high mean value of 3.15 and ranked 1st while the least was indicator 2, "Does the school canteen was supplied with enough chairs and tables for its operation?", with mean of 2.87 interpreted as "agree" and ranked 5th. Overall, the responses towards policies obtained a weighted mean of 3.04 with the qualitative interpretation of "agree".

2.3 Staff Management

Table 5 shows the perception of the respondents towards Staff Management affecting the operation of the school canteen.

Table 5
Perception towards Staff Management Affecting Operation of School Canteen

Statement Indicator	WM	QI	Rank
1. Does the school canteen staff supervise properly and encouraged personal development?	3.21	A	1
2. Does the school canteen staffs maintain a working environment that is conducive to work?	3.10	A	3
3. Does the school canteen staff were given equipment like uniforms and aprons that are important to the service?	3.17	A	2
4. Does the school canteen staff were provided with employee benefits for their welfare?	3.07	A	4
5. Is there a strong coordination and system of communication among the school canteen staff?	3.05	A	5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.12	A	

The respondents "Agree" on indicator 1, "Does the school canteen staff supervise properly and encouraged personal development?", manifested in its high mean value of 3.21 and ranked 1st while the least was indicator 5, "Is there a strong coordination and system of communication among the school canteen staff?", with mean of 3.05 interpreted as "agree" and ranked 5th. Overall, the responses towards staff management obtained a weighted mean of 3.12 with the qualitative interpretation of "agree".

3. Factors/Contributors affecting Quality of School Canteen Services

3.1 Assessment of Food Quality Services

Table 6 shows the perception of the respondents towards the assessment of food quality services affecting the quality of school canteen services.

The respondents were "Strongly satisfied" with indicator 1, "Offered foods were fresh, clean and nutritious.", manifested in its high mean value of 3.27 and ranked 1st while the least was indicator 4, "There was an established partnership by the administration to commercial food concessionaires", with mean of 3.11 interpreted as "satisfied" and ranked 5th. Overall, the responses towards Sanitation obtained a weighted mean of 3.15 with the qualitative interpretation of "satisfied".

Table 6

Perception towards Assessment of Food Quality Services affecting Quality of School Canteen Services

Statement Indicator	WM	QI	Rank
1. Canteen staffs are approachable and pleasant to patrons.	3.20	Strongly Satisfied	1
2. There are enough staffs to attend the number of students, faculty, and staff.	2.94	Satisfied	5
3. Services are timely.	3.10	Satisfied	3
4. Canteen staff maintain the order of operation of the food services.	3.08	Satisfied	4
5. The canteen operators ensure that there is enough supply of food for every patron.	3.13	Satisfied	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.09	S	

3.2 Quality Services

Table 7 shows the perception of the respondents towards quality services affecting the quality of school canteen services.

Table 7

Perception towards Quality Services Affecting Quality of School Canteen Services

Statement Indicator	WM	QI	Rank
6. Canteen staffs are approachable and pleasant to patrons.	3.20	Strongly Satisfied	1
7. There are enough staffs to attend the number of students, faculty, and staff.	2.94	Satisfied	5
8. Services are timely.	3.10	Satisfied	3
9. Canteen staff maintain the order of operation of the food services.	3.08	Satisfied	4
10. The canteen operators ensure that there is enough supply of food for every patron.	3.13	Satisfied	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.09	S	

The respondents were "Strongly satisfied" with indicator 1, "Canteen staffs are approachable and pleasant to patrons", manifested in its high mean value of 3.20 and ranked 1st while the least was indicator 4, "There are enough staffs to attend numbers of students, faculty, and staffs.", with mean of 2.94 interpreted as "satisfied" and ranked 5th. Overall, the responses towards Sanitation obtained a weighted mean of 3.09 with the qualitative interpretation of "satisfied".

4. Importance of Canteen Operation

Table 8 shows the perception of the respondents towards the importance of having a school canteen.

The respondents rated "Very important" indicator 2, "A school canteen can offer nutritious, nicely presented food and drinks at a fair price and support classroom learning", manifested in its high mean value of 3.34 and ranked 1st while the least was indicator 3, "Parental participation in the school community, especially at the canteen, can be quite rewarding for both parties involved.", with mean of 3.18 interpreted as "important" and ranked 5th. Overall, the responses towards Sanitation obtained a weighted mean of 3.24 with the qualitative interpretation of "important".

Table 8
Perception towards the Importance of Having a School Canteen

Statement Indicator	WM	QI	Rank
1. The school community may be able to benefit from the services provided by the school canteen.	3.26	Very Important	2
2. A school canteen can offer nutritious, nicely presented food and drinks at a fair price and support classroom learning.	3.34	Very Important	1
3. Parental participation in the school community, especially at the canteen, can be quite rewarding for both parties involved.	3.18	Important	5
4. School canteens can be an important source of nutrition and business education that complements classroom learning and a whole-school approach to healthy eating, such as the school vegetable garden.	3.21	Important	3
5. School canteens can also contribute funds to schools.	3.20	Important	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.24	I	

5. Summary of Test of Differences on the Perception Towards Operation of School Canteen

Table 9 shows the analysis of variance (ANOVA/F-test) to test differences in the perception towards the operation of the school canteen of student-respondents when grouped according to grade level profile variables.

Table 9
Analysis of Variance to Test Differences in the Respondent's Perceptions towards the Operation of the School Canteen when Grouped According to Grade Level Profile Variables

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Sanitation	Between Groups	.001	1	.001	.005	.943	Accepted H ₀ Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.305	68	.169			
	Total	11.306	69				
Policies	Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.001	.975	Accepted H ₀ Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.716	68	.160			
	Total	10.717	69				
Staff Management	Between Groups	.002	1	.002	.017	.897	Accepted H ₀ Not Significant
	Within Groups	7.695	68	.115			
	Total	7.697	69				

The respondents perceived "not significant" manifested on the P-value of 0.943, 0.975, and 0.897 higher than (>) 0.05 alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the perception towards sanitation, policies, and staff management when grouped according to grade level profile variables.

6. Summary of Test of Differences on the Perception Towards Quality of Canteen Services

Table 10 shows the analysis of variance (ANOVA/F-test) to test differences in the perception towards the quality of services provided by the canteen of Students- respondents when grouped according to Grade level profile variables.

Table 10
Analysis of Variance to Test Differences on the Respondent's Perceptions towards Quality Services Provided by the Canteen when Grouped According to Grade Level Profile Variables

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Quality of Food	Between Groups	.197	1	.197	1.174	.282	Accepted H ₀ Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.265	68	.168			
	Total	11.462	69				
Quality of Services	Between Groups	.374	1	.374	2.274	.136	Accepted H ₀ Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.032	68	.165			
	Total	11.406	69				
Importance	Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.001	.971	Accepted H ₀ Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.606	68	.158			
	Total	10.606	69				

The respondents perceived "not significant" manifested on the P-value of 0.282, 0.136, and 0.971 higher than (>) 0.05 alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the perception towards the quality of food, quality of services, and importance of school canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables.

7. Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to Test Relationship Between Operation of School Canteen and Quality of Canteen Services

Table 11 shows the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to test the relationship between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services.

Table 11

Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to Test the Relationship Between the Operation of School Canteen and the Quality of Canteen Services

Sources of Variation		Quality of services	Operation of School Canteen
quality_services	Pearson Correlation	1	.736**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	69	69
operation	Pearson Correlation	.736**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	69	69

There is a high correlation between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services manifested in the computed Pearson r-value of 0.736. The computed significant P-value of 0.000 is lower than (<) 0.05 alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant relationship.

Discussion

1. Profile of the Respondents

The data suggest that there had been equal distribution of respondents taken from Grades 11 and 12 in the Senior High School.

2. Factors/Contributors Affecting the Operation of the School Canteen

2.1 Sanitation

The data indicate the SHS students agreed that the school canteen practiced a standard and good practice of sanitation in their operations, particularly in maintaining cleanliness and following health and safety protocols, as well as following the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for hygiene practices.

2.2 Policies

The data indicate the SHS students agreed that the school canteen followed the prescribed policies on the standard operation of the school canteen, particularly on hiring qualified personnel, inspection, and general operations.

2.3 Staff Management

The data indicate the SHS students agreed that the school canteen practiced a standard and good practice of sanitation in their operations, particularly in maintaining cleanliness and following health and safety protocols, as well as following the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for hygiene practices.

3. Factors/Contributors affecting Quality of School Canteen Services

3.1 Assessment of Food Quality Services

The data suggest further that the SHS students are satisfied with the food quality services of the school canteen, particularly in preparing and serving food that is fresh, clean, and nutritious; handling; pricing; preparing menu; and concessionaries.

3.2 Quality Services

The data reveal further that the SHS students are satisfied with the quality services of the school canteen operation, particularly with staffing, food services, and supply management.

4. Importance of Canteen Operation

The data indicate further that the SHS students acknowledged the importance of having a school canteen in school operations, especially in serving the school community and providing nutritious and healthy meals.

5. Summary of Test of Differences on the Perception Towards Operation of School Canteen

The data indicate that Grades 11 and 12 students have statistically the same level of assessment on the operations of the school canteen which is acceptable on their part; hence, they both agreed on the quality of operation of the school canteen.

6. Summary of Test of Differences on the Perception Towards Quality of Canteen Services

The data indicate that Grades 11 and 12 students have statistically the same level of assessment on the quality services of operation of the school canteen which is acceptable on their part; hence, they both agreed on the quality services of operation of the school canteen.

7. Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to Test Relationship Between Operation of School Canteen and Quality of Canteen Services

Table 11 shows the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to test the relationship between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services.

The data indicate further that as the quality of services increases, the operation of the school canteen also increases; hence, indicating a positive relationship between the two variables.

8. Strategic Plan for the Operation of the School Canteen

The results indicate that the school canteen operations and services are satisfactory to the learners, as well as important to them; hence, there is also a need to continuously sustain its operational and service quality in general. Initiatives for such shall conform to the standards of healthy food and beverages (DO 13, s. 2017), food safety in schools (DO 52, s. 2008), and school canteen management and operations (DO 8, s. 2007). Ensuring adherence to such institutional policies guarantees that quality services and operations are provided to the school community and to the learners at large.

In accordance with the said insights, the strategic plan for the operation of the school canteen is presented below:

Objectives	Strategic Measures	Resources Needed	Timeframe	Persons Involved	Expected Outcomes
To sustain and elevate the quality practices of school canteen operations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultative meeting with the stakeholder of the school/canteen clientele Partner with food concessionaries Conduct feedback on the quality of operations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting forms MOU/MOA Feedback forms 	All-year round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Canteen Manager Canteen Staff Industry-Partners Clientele 	<p>Sustained quality of school canteen operations</p> <p>Enhanced collaboration for quality school canteen operations</p>

<p>To sustain and elevate the quality practices of the services provided by the school canteen.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultative meeting with the stakeholder of the school/canteen clientele • Partner with food concessionaries • Provide feedback mechanisms to improve services • Conduct a survey for menu preparations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting forms • MOU/MOA • Feedback forms • Survey forms 	<p>All-year round</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Canteen Manager • Canteen Staff • Industry-Partners • Clientele 	<p>Sustained quality services provided by the school canteen.</p> <p>Enhanced partnership for improving quality services of school canteen</p>
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Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

- There are (69) sixty-nine respondents who are from Grade 11 and Grade 12 of the Senior High School.
- The student-respondents agreed on the factors/contributors affecting the operation of the school canteen such as sanitation, policies, and staff management.
- The student-respondents are satisfied with the factors/contributors affecting the quality of school canteen services in terms of the assessment of food quality services and quality services.
- The student-respondents acknowledged the importance of having a school canteen in school operations, especially in serving the school community and providing nutritious and healthy meals.
- There are no significant differences in the respondent’s perceptions towards the operation of the school canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables.
- There are no significant differences in the respondent’s perceptions towards quality services provided by the canteen when grouped according to grade level profile variables.
- There is a positive correlation between the operation of the school canteen and the quality of canteen services.
- The study proposed a strategic plan to improve further the operation of the school canteen to cater to the needs of the clientele, especially the SHS students on its operation and services provided.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

- More SHS students can be summoned further to participate in a wide-scale survey to provide comprehensive detail on their perceptions of school canteen operations and services.
- A robust monitoring of the school canteen operation can be initiated to ensure that emerging issues or challenges to maintain a high level of operation can be achieved.
- A robust monitoring of the school canteen’s provision of quality services can be initiated to ensure that emerging issues or challenges to maintain a high level of services provided to the clientele.
- An information dissemination to reiterate the importance of the school canteen to provide quality services to the school community and to the learners to ensure that everyone is involved in the solicitation of needs improvement.
- In the provision of ensuring quality operations of the school canteen, perceptions of student-clientele shall be solicited further for a more comprehensive and responsive approach to needs improvement.
- In the provision of ensuring quality services of the school canteen, perceptions of student-clientele shall be solicited further for a more comprehensive and responsive approach to needs improvement.
- In the provision of quality operations and services of the school canteen, the factors and their relationships with one another shall always be considered for optimal outcomes.
- The developed strategic plan shall be cascaded and evaluated further to ensure its effectiveness and responsiveness to the needs of the clientele, thus, establishing further areas for improvements.

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